

OPTIMIZING INVENTORY MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES TO PREVENT ANTIRETROVIRAL (ARV) MEDICINE SHORTAGES IN HEALTH INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CENTRAL MEDICAL STORES AND MEDICAL RESCUE INTERNATIONAL BOTSWANA

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Abstract

This study explores the role of inventory management strategies in ensuring the availability of antiretroviral (ARV) medicines in health institutions. It investigates the effectiveness of these systems in addressing shortages by collecting data through interviews with representatives from the Central Medical Stores (CMS) in Gaborone West Industrial and Medical Rescue International Botswana (MRIB). Both institutions utilize distinct inventory management systems, and respondents concur that these systems have been instrumental in eliminating shortages. The occasional shortages encountered are attributed to logistical challenges in order processing rather than inefficiencies in the systems themselves. MRIB, operating under a retail license, faces additional challenges in procuring medicines from warehouse operators, further exacerbating shortages due to supplier acquisition difficulties. To mitigate shortages, both institutions collaborate by requesting supplies from each other, referring patients to other institutions, or temporarily changing medications. Neither CMS nor MRIB maintains buffer stock; instead, CMS undertakes a quantification process six to twelve months prior to ordering, with procurement dependent on whether the medication is sourced locally or internationally. MRIB, with a lead time of one to two days, orders from wholesalers as needed. Although not keeping safety stock reduces operational costs and prevents obsolete stock, implementing a two-bin inventory management system could further eliminate shortages. This system would ensure a continuous supply of medication, thereby minimizing disruptions in ARV provision.

Keywords: Inventory Management, Antiretroviral Medicines, Health Institutions, ARV Shortages, Logistics, Two-Bin System, Supply Chain Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines essential medications as those that address the most pressing health requirements of a population (Bigdeli, Laing, Tomson, & Babar, 2015). These medications form the backbone of public health initiatives aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality (Pecoul, 1999). Antiretroviral (ARV) drugs are classified as essential in Botswana due to their critical role in managing HIV/AIDS, a significant health crisis preceding the COVID-19 pandemic. ARVs function by inhibiting the replication of the HIV virus within the body, allowing the immune system to repair itself and prevent further damage. While ARVs do not cure HIV, they significantly extend the lifespan of individuals who adhere to their prescribed regimens.

Automating inventory management is one of the effective strategies health centers can employ to maintain accurate records of their ARV stock levels (Turns, 2023). Implementing systems such as barcodes or radio frequency identification (RFID) can streamline the tracking process, ensuring timely reordering of supplies. Accurate setting of reorder points is also crucial to prevent stockouts and minimize the risk of theft or expiration of obsolete stock. Moreover, maintaining buffer or safety stock is vital for health centers to accommodate fluctuations in patient demand, including newly diagnosed individuals requiring immediate treatment (Gemechu, Ayalew, Tefera, Mulugeta, & Bekele, 2021). Ensuring a consistent supply of ARVs is essential for the effective management of HIV/AIDS, thereby supporting the health and longevity of affected populations.

1.1 Problem Statement

The third National Multi-Sectoral Strategic Framework for HIV (2018–2023) in Botswana emphasizes expanding antiretroviral treatment and revitalizing HIV combination prevention. Botswana is well-positioned to meet the UNAIDS 95–95–95 targets, which aim for 95% of individuals living with HIV to know their status, 95% of those aware to receive treatment, and 95% of those receiving treatment to achieve viral suppression, ultimately ending the AIDS pandemic by 2030 (Chowdhury, 2023). To sustain these accomplishments, continuous surveillance is critical to identifying potential challenges to epidemic control, including treatment disruptions. This is where effective inventory management strategies are vital to ensuring no shortages or disruptions in ARV provision, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 3: good health and well-being.

1.2 General Objective of the Study

This research aims to explore how inventory management strategies can be utilized to help Botswana achieve the UNAIDS 95–95–95 target and end the AIDS pandemic by 2030. The focus is on ensuring continuous and timely delivery of ARV drugs to prevent any interruptions in patient treatment. Additionally, the study seeks to evaluate whether these strategies enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of ARV provision.

1.3 Research Objectives

- i. To assess the effectiveness of inventory management systems in optimizing ARV stock levels to prevent both overstocking and stockouts.
- ii. To identify methods for maintaining the quality and safety of ARV medicines, with an emphasis on handling procedures and storage conditions.
- iii. To explore strategies for reducing costs through efficient inventory management practices.
- iv. To examine how inventory management strategies can adapt to fluctuating demand for ARV medicines.

1.4 Research Questions

- i. How can inventory management systems be leveraged to optimize ARV stock levels, ensuring a balance that avoids both overstocking and stockouts?
- ii. What measures can be taken to ensure the quality and safety of ARV medications, focusing on handling procedures and storage conditions?
- iii. What approaches can be implemented to achieve cost reduction through cost-effective inventory management practices?
- iv. How can inventory management strategies be adapted to accommodate fluctuating or changing demand for ARV medications?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of the History of ARV Inventory Management

The supply of prescription drugs held in reserve to satisfy future demand is referred to as inventory in pharmacy operations (Ali & Ferguson, 2011). In pharmacy practice, inventory is the most valuable asset, increasingly so due to the growing variety and expense of pharmaceutical items. The goal of an efficient health procurement system is to provide appropriate, well-recognized medications at fair rates and in the appropriate quantities. Effective inventory management benefits pharmacy practice both financially and operationally by reducing procurement and carrying costs while maintaining a sufficient supply to meet customer and prescriber demand (Ayad, 2011).

One of the biggest issues facing Botswana's health system is the intermittent availability of basic supplies, including commodities and medications. Stockouts and shortages influence the provision of healthcare services throughout the nation. Medicine shortages create significant obstacles to healthcare, leading to therapeutic disparities, safety concerns (such as compromised outcomes, prescription errors, and deaths), and financial repercussions (such as increased hospital charges, labor costs, and patient costs) (Kgosietsile, 2022). National procurement systems frequently struggle to negotiate the best pricing for commodities, necessitating larger orders while remaining adaptable to the changing needs of healthcare facilities (Bishen & Spina, 2023). Several nations have opted for pooled procurement to obtain lower unit costs for necessary medications. Pooled procurement, sometimes referred to as joint purchasing, is a cooperative approach in which many purchasers pool their purchases to strengthen their market position and negotiate better terms (Domfeh, 2021). Pooled procurement of medicines ensures a consistent and sustainable supply of appropriate medicines at the national and district levels. It is increasingly regarded globally as an efficient strategy to address challenges such as high medicine prices, poor quality, and other bottlenecks generally associated with procurement and supply chains of essential medicines and medical supplies (Larson, 2014).

Currently, Botswana does not manufacture pharmaceuticals domestically. The Ministry of Health and Central Medical Stores (CMS) handle the procurement of necessary medications for the public health sector. Under this arrangement, the designated government body oversees acquiring, stockpiling, and distributing public health supplies, including ARVs. CMS anticipates, purchases, and distributes Botswana's medications, medical equipment, and immunizations based on historical forecasting, using previous year's data to guide its projections (Montsho, 2021). Inadequate medication flow monitoring can result in obsolete stock, such as expired or underused medications, which prevents medications from being available and hinders patients from achieving their therapeutic objectives. CMS performance is determined by product availability and expiry rates (Clark & Barraclough, 2010). Product availability shows the assortment of goods that healthcare facilities can obtain from CMS, supporting ongoing patient care. Minimum product expiration dates are necessary in some cases to guarantee availability, but excessive expiries waste resources and indicate system flaws. CMS reports the percentage of medication "stock" items in central inventory for at least a month, divided into vital, essential, and non-essential categories. Goals are set at 97% availability for vital, 80% for essential, and 80% for non-essential items. Poor coordination and communication between CMS and service consumers have harmed the drug delivery system. Visibility of demand data from service delivery sites is essential to a robust supply system and needs prioritization. CMS has faced criticism for disorganized distribution, inadequate customer service, false stock records, and infrequent deliveries, which erode trust in CMS's professionalism and moral character.

2.2 Evaluating Other Studies

According to Rodrigues (2021), researchers can examine study methodologies and compare and assess facts and information to evaluate the effectiveness of inventory management systems. Gemechu (2021) assessed inventory data to determine its accuracy and timeliness. Results showed that, on average, 90.6% of bin card data were accurate, surpassing the minimum target of 80%. However, discrepancies between hospitals and health centers in accurate stock on hand data may lead to unsustainable stockouts, arising from varying sample sizes and local performance. Manual inventory monitoring techniques are prone to frequent errors, leading to ARV shortages and contradicting health institutions' goals to reduce disruptions and achieve the UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets (Barratt et al., 2018). Iacob and Jugulete (2017) elucidated that ARV medicine needs are unpredictable, posing a serious risk to patients' lives due to stockouts. They suggested a stochastic inventory management system for ARV medications, which considers the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Optimal Re-order Point (ROP), and ideal buffer stock size. This model takes into account the total cost per unit time of ordering, maintaining buffer stock, and inventory costs for each ARV medication. The study aims to provide data to help the ART program administration make decisions to prevent medication stock-outs. Unlike other models, this approach considers both buffer stock amount and cost, solving problems of obsolescent inventory and saving funds through optimal ordering. This model is suitable for aiding Botswana's health institutions in managing their inventory effectively and efficiently.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research will employ a mixed-methods approach to data collection. According to Steynberg (2017), mixed-methods research integrates both qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. This approach combines various techniques for data collection, analysis, and inference to enhance corroboration and achieve a broad and deep understanding of the subject.

3.1 Research Design

A correlational research design is most appropriate for this study. As McCombes (2012) describes, correlational research aims to identify the relationship between two or more variables. This study seeks to explore the correlation between purchasing practices and inventory management strategies, and their effectiveness in addressing the gaps in ARV provision and supply. By comparing different inventory management strategies, the research aims to identify the most effective approach for improving efficiency and effectiveness in health institutions.

3.2 Population of Study

The study will be conducted at Central Medical Stores (CMS) and Medical Rescue International Botswana (MRI), both of which are involved in medication dispensing. Participants will include procurement officers, transport and logistics staff (including drivers) from CMS, and pharmacists from MRI. The procurement department's involvement is crucial as it handles the tendering process, affecting supplier selection and lead time, which in turn influences inventory management strategies. Transport and logistics personnel will provide insights into consignment handling, storage, and current inventory management practices. Pharmacists will offer perspectives on how ARV shortages are managed and their impact on patients. Two officers from each department will be interviewed, though additional staff may also be consulted to enrich the data.

3.3 Sampling Procedure

The research will use non-probability sampling due to the unpredictable availability of participants. Specifically, convenience sampling will be employed, where participants are selected based on their proximity and availability to the researcher. This method is chosen for its practicality, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency.

Table 1: Sampling of Participants

INSTITUTION	DEPARTMENT	NUMBER OF OFFICERS
Medical Rescue International	Pharmacists	2
Central Medical Stores	Procurement	2
Central Medical Stores	Driver	2
TOTAL		6

3.4 Instrumentation

The researcher will utilize interviews as the primary data collection method for this study, as opposed to questionnaires, which might limit the depth and breadth of information participants can provide. The interviews will focus on several key areas: the current inventory management systems employed by the institutions, their effectiveness in addressing ARV shortages, the volume of ARV consignments handled, and any issues related to obsolescence or medication expiration. Additional questions will address how medication shortages are managed and the order processing procedures. Medical Rescue International, as a private entity, will provide valuable insights into the number of new patients and how these figures are used to estimate the appropriate amount of buffer or safety stock needed. Driver's job cards, which record trips to suppliers and associated times, will aid in estimating lead times, impacting inventory management decisions. Purchase order files will help verify the amount ordered and its adequacy in meeting patient needs, thus preventing shortages.

3.5 Data Collection

Data will be collected through structured interviews, as defined by Responsible Conduct in Data Management (2023) as a deliberate exchange of questions and answers between participants. The researcher will prepare a set of structured questions in advance, addressing topics such as the current inventory management systems used by the institution, estimation of new patient numbers, current patient enrollment, monthly shortage reports, and storage precautions to extend medication usage and reduce theft. Additionally, information will be gathered from job cards and purchase request documents.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Participants in this research study will be required to sign a consent form, indicating their voluntary participation without coercion. The study is conducted for educational purposes, and participants need not worry about unauthorized dissemination of institutional information. Participants are encouraged to contact the researcher with any questions, ensuring transparency. Only institutional names will be used in the study to maintain anonymity, and personal information of participants will remain confidential. Data encryption will be employed to protect against unauthorized access.

3.7 Data Analysis and Data Presentation

The primary objective of this study is to assess whether inventory management systems effectively eliminate ARV medication shortages in health institutions. Given Botswana's Vision 2036 goals and the UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets, as well as the Sustainable Development Goals, it is crucial for the country to eliminate medication shortages to protect public health and contain the spread of HIV.

Figure 1: Interview Questions for Central Medical Stores

The information presented is based on data from the Central Medical Stores (CMS), which has utilized the Pulse system for inventory management since 2014. This system tracks both incoming and outgoing inventory, recording the quantities of stock received from pharmaceutical suppliers and distributed to hospitals and clinics. According to the respondents, CMS does not maintain buffer stock but employs a quantification process that begins 6 to 12 months prior to procurement to mitigate potential shortages. The lead time, which is 17.9%, varies depending on the order's origin and procurement source. While CMS sources some medication from local pharmaceuticals—who, in turn, may also acquire their stock from external suppliers—there are occasions when CMS imports medications from abroad, including the United States, Russia, or India. CMS does not handle direct patient care; instead, it supplies public hospitals and clinics. Despite a potential 12.3% chance of encountering shortages, these are effectively managed through collaboration with other health institutions and by providing a two-month inventory coverage to the health posts it supplies, thus minimizing the impact of shortages.

Figure 2: Interview Questions for Med-Rescue

MEDRESCUE International Botswana (MRIB), like Central Medical Stores, coordinates with other institutions during shortages and may adjust patients' medication to align with

available stock, provided there is consent from both patients and doctors. MRIB utilizes the Conformer inventory management system, with 17.0% of respondents endorsing its effectiveness in mitigating shortage issues within the institution. According to the respondents, MRIB operates under a retail license and does not maintain an in-house stock of medications; instead, it acquires drugs for patient sales, which leads to shortages as the institution must source medications from various wholesalers. This situation affects the lead time and reflects the institution's status as a private entity serving 7.7% of its clients. The charts presented offer insights into responses related to shortages, revealing the institution's strategies for managing these challenges. The data indicates that MRIB does not maintain buffer stock, as demonstrated by the percentage of responses shown in the charts. This lack of buffer stock is consistent across various questions posed during the interviews. Additionally, the respondents' answers address the research objectives effectively.

Objective 1

To evaluate the effectiveness of inventory management systems in optimizing ARV stock levels, ensuring equilibrium between overstocking and stockouts. The Pulse system, known for its optimized ordering recommendations, including maximum and minimum order calculations, helps maintain accurate inventory levels, preventing both excess and shortages. Respondents confirm that these systems effectively mitigate disruptions in medication provision, achieving equilibrium. Similarly, the Conformer inventory management system used by Medical Rescue International (MRIB) enhances stock level management and provides real-time insights.

Objective 2

To assess how quality and safety are ensured in ARV provision, including handling procedures and storage conditions. Both institutions do not maintain safety or buffer stock, thereby reducing the risk of theft or obsolescence. Inventory is handled promptly upon purchase order arrival, ensuring immediate distribution to patients, thus maintaining quality and safety.

Objective 3

To investigate how cost reduction can be achieved through cost-effective inventory management practices. The absence of safety stock has already mitigated many shortages. Additionally, the quantification process, which begins 6 to 12 months before ordering, minimizes errors by providing ample time for preparation, further reducing costs.

Objective 4

To examine how inventory management strategies accommodate fluctuating or changing demand. Medical Rescue International does not experience significant demand fluctuations, minimizing issues in medication ordering. Central Medical Stores, serving nationwide hospitals and clinics, also experiences minimal demand fluctuations, though errors in data exchange can occur, potentially affecting inventory levels.

3.8 Summary of the Study

As Botswana aims to enhance life expectancy and combat communicable diseases like HIV/AIDS, the swift provision of antiretroviral medication without shortages is crucial. The study, through seven interview questions, evaluates whether health institutions are positioned to achieve this goal by 2036, focusing on the effectiveness of inventory management systems. Findings aim to determine if these systems effectively prevent ARV shortages and how shortages are managed if they occur.

4. DISCUSSIONS

In line with Tessema (2022), the study highlights the importance of logistical tools for data collection and decision-making. The effectiveness of inventory management systems, such as Pulse and Conformer, is confirmed by the interviewed institutions. Gurmu (2017) supports the study's findings, indicating that while logistical challenges cause shortages, the systems themselves are effective. Both institutions manage shortages by requesting supplies from pharmaceutical companies or altering patient medication temporarily. Despite not maintaining safety stock, the systems in place ensure timely medication provision, although issues like theft and obsolescence can still arise. The study also notes that data collection errors and patient fluctuations can impact inventory levels. Nonetheless, the systems' ability to handle these challenges effectively is acknowledged.

4.1 Conclusions

Inventory management systems play a critical role in managing ARV distribution and are effective in supporting UNAIDS 95-95-95 targets, Sustainable Development Goals, and Vision 2036. Respondents affirm the systems' role in ensuring timely medication provision and achieving these health goals.

4.2 Recommendations

1. Health institutions should collaborate with researchers to enhance healthcare systems while maintaining patient confidentiality.
2. Both institutions should consider adopting the two-bin inventory management system to address issues related to logistical delays and ensure continuous medication supply.
3. Institutions should build stronger relationships with domestic pharmaceutical companies to reduce lead times and reliance on international purchases.
4. Further research should explore the impact of patient fluctuations on ARV provision and evaluate the adaptability of inventory management systems in a dynamic environment.
5. CMS and MRIB should continuously review and update their inventory management strategies to accommodate evolving technology and patient needs.

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